

Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium and Ruthenium with N-Benzoyl-N'-Methylphenyl Selenourea

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N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea is recommended as a chelating agent for the spectrophotometric determination of osmium(VI) and ruthenium(III). It forms a wine red complex with osmium(VI) which can be quantitatively extracted with chloroform at pH 4.20-5.50. The reagent forms a reddish-brown complex with ruthenium(III). Quantitative extraction of ruthenium is obtained from a solution at 0.8M-3.0M hydrochloric acid. The chloroform extracts of both osmium and ruthenium complexes show maximum absorption at 460 nm and Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration ranging from 2.83 μg to 28.30 μg Os(VI)/ml and 0.65 to 9.81 μg Ru(III)/ml. The reagent forms 2:1 and 3:1 complexes with osmium and ruthenium respectively. The advantage of the use of N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea as a spectrophotometric reagent for both osmium and ruthenium lies in the fact that these metal ions can be determined in presence of all base metals and large excess of all other platinum metals. Simultaneous determination of osmium and ruthenium is possible with the chelating agent.

THIOUREA and several substituted thioureas¹⁻⁶ were used for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum metals. The platinum metals prefer the ligands having polarizable centre specially where back-bonding is possible. This condition favours selenium containing ligands which can be explained from the theoretical stand point. The dianion Se^{-2} (1.95 Å) would be more easily polarized because of its larger ionic radius than sulphur dianion S^{-2} (1.84 Å). Again, under favourable conditions the vacant 4d orbitals of selenium being probably of lower energy are suitable for back-bonding. Goddard⁷ *et al* have determined the stability of metal complexes of selenourea, seleno-semicarbazide as well as thiourea, thiosemicarbazide and found that selenium has greater affinity towards the class 'b' (platinum metals) than sulphur. Pilipenko and Sereda⁸⁻¹⁰ first studied the analytical aspects of substituted selenoureas and selenoures for the determination of metals. Disubstituted selenoureas¹¹ have been introduced very recently as ligands for the platinum metals. In the present investigation N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea is introduced as a selective reagent for the determination and separation of micro amounts of osmium and ruthenium. It forms a wine red complex with osmium(VI) in hot acetate medium which can be fully extracted with chloroform at pH 4.20-5.50. Ruthenium(III) reacts with the reagent in hot dilute hydrochloric acid medium forming a reddish-brown complex which is quantitatively extracted with chloroform. The advantage of the use of N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea as a spectrophotometric reagent for osmium and ruthenium lies in the fact that these metal ions can be determined in the presence of all base metals and

large excess of all other platinum metals. Simultaneous determination of osmium and ruthenium is also possible with this chelating agent.

Apparatus: A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer PMQII type equipped with one cm quartz cells was used for the transmittance measurements. All the pH measurements were carried out with a Cambridge pH meter (Bench model).

Reagent and Chemicals: Preparation and properties of N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea.

N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea was prepared by the following method as described by Douglass^{1,2}: Benzoylisoselenocyanate was obtained by adding 0.1 mole benzoyl chloride to a solution of 0.1M mole of potassium selenocyanate in 200 ml of acetone. An exothermic reaction took place with the separation of potassium chloride, which was filtered. To the filtrate 0.1 mole of monomethyl aniline in 100 ml of acetone was added as rapidly as the vigorous boiling of the reaction mixture would permit. When the reaction had subsided, the mixture was poured slowly with stirring into 630-800 ml of cold water. The solid selenourea which separated was removed by filtration. The crude yellow mass was recrystallized several times from 50% ethanol using a small quantity of charcoal. N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea was thus obtained as pale yellow shining crystals (m.p. 120-121°). The compound is appreciably stable towards heat, light, air and non-oxidising acid. On prolonged exposure to air the compound exhibits reddish colour due to decomposition.

Reagent solution : A 0.01M solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of dried and recrystallized N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea in ethanol and the volume was made up to the mark by adding more ethanol.

Standard metal solutions : Osmic acid was dissolved in 0.1M sodium hydroxide and was standardized by precipitating the metal as sulphide, which was then ignited in a current of hydrogen to be weighed as metal. The standard solution of ruthenium was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of the corresponding chloride in dilute hydrochloric acid and the metal content of the solution was determined by precipitating with thiosalicylamide^{1,2}. Weaker solutions of the metals for the spectrophotometric determination were prepared by proper dilution of the stock solution. The solution of osmium was preserved in cold.

The standard solutions of the metals used to study the effect of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of their salts in distilled water. Dilute hydrochloric acid was added where required. Solutions of anions were prepared from their respective alkali metal salts.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure :

Osmium : A known volume of the osmium solution containing about 250 μg of metal was placed in a 100 ml separatory funnel. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 4.20 and 5.50 by the addition of 10% sodium acetate solution and dilute hydrochloric acid. To this, 3 ml of reagent solution (0.01M) were added and thoroughly mixed. The mixture was warmed on a boiling water bath for 5 minutes. The wine red precipitate formed was extracted with chloroform. The total volume of the extract was made to 25 ml with chloroform and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 460 nm against a reagent blank prepared under similar conditions.

Ruthenium : A measured amount of the ruthenium solution was taken into a 100 ml separatory funnel and the solution was made 1M-3M in respect of hydrochloric acid. To this, 2 ml of the reagent solution (0.01M) were added and thoroughly mixed. The mixture was warmed on a boiling water bath for half an hour. The reddish brown precipitate was extracted with chloroform. The volume was made to 25 ml with chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 460 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves : The absorbance curves of the solutions of osmium and ruthenium complexes are shown in Fig. 1. The chloroform extracts of

Fig. 1.1. Absorbance curves of Osmium-N-Benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl-selenourea complex in chloroform. [Os]: I=3.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, II=6.16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, III=7.70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$

Fig. 1.2. Absorbance curves of Ruthenium-N-Benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea complex in Chloroform. [Ru]: I=3.27 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, II=4.896 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, III=6.54 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$

both osmium and ruthenium complexes show maximum absorbance at 460 nm, where the reagent has practically no absorption.

Effect of acidity : The acidities of the osmium and ruthenium solutions were adjusted by adding 10% sodium acetate solution and dilute hydrochloric

acid. After extraction of the metal complexes, the acidities of the aqueous layers were measured either by titrating against a standard alkali or with the aid of a pH meter. It was observed that ruthenium was completely extracted when the solution was 0.8-3.0M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The extraction of osmium was quantitative between pH 4.20 and 5.50.

Stability of colour : The colour of the chloroform extracts of the metal complexes was found to be stable for 24 hours, after which it slowly faded.

Conformity to Beer's law : It was observed that the Beer's law holds good at 460 nm over the concentration of osmium and ruthenium ranging from $2.83 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ to $28.30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and from $0.56 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ to $9.81 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively.

Nature of metal complexes in solution : The empirical formulae of osmium and ruthenium complexes formed with N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea were determined by the mole-ratio method¹⁴. The results indicate that the chelating agent forms 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 complexes with osmium and ruthenium respectively. These compositions were verified by the slope-ratio method.

Sensitivity, Molar Extinction Co-efficient and Optimum Concentration range for Photometry of Osmium and Ruthenium : The sensitivities, molar extinction co-efficients of osmium and ruthenium complexes and optimum concentration ranges for the determination of these two metals are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—MOLAR EXTINCTION CO-EFFICIENT, SENSITIVITY AND OPTIMUM CONCENTRATION RANGE FOR PHOTOMETRY OF RUTHENIUM AND OSMIUM

Ruthenium		Osmium			
Wave length nm.	Molar extinction coefficient cm^{-1} μg^{-1} l mole^{-1}	Optimum concentration range $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Wave length nm.	Molar extinction coefficient cm^{-1} μg^{-1} l mole^{-1}	Optimum concentration range $\mu\text{g/ml}$
460	6.93×10^3	0.015-5.46	460	8.123×10^3	0.023-22.22

Effect of diverse ions :

Osmium(VI) and ruthenium(III) were determined with N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea in presence of known amounts of large numbers of diverse ions, following the procedure described above. Interferences of most of the base metals were avoided by using E.D.T.A. or tartrate. Interference of ruthenium in the determination of osmium was avoided by prior extraction of ruthenium at 2M hydrochloric acid. All the other platinum metals did not interfere with the determination

TABLE 2.—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF OSMIUM(VI) AND RUTHENIUM(III)

Osmium (212.25 μg)		Ruthenium (183.40 μg)	
Diverse ions	Amount tolerated (μg)	Diverse ions	Amount tolerated (μg)
E.D.T.A.	5000	E.D.T.A.	5000
Tartrate	5000	Tartrate	5000
PO_4^{3-}	7000	PO_4^{3-}	7000
F^-	7000	F^-	7000
Mn^{2+}	1000 ^b	Mn^{2+}	1000
Ni^{2+}	1000 ^b	Ni^{2+}	1000
Co^{2+}	1000 ^b	Co^{2+}	1000
Cd^{2+}	1500 ^b	Cd^{2+}	1500
Zn^{2+}	2000 ^b	Zn^{2+}	2000
Fe^{3+}	2000 ^a	Fe^{3+}	2000
Al^{3+}	1000 ^b	Al^{3+}	1500
Cr^{3+}	1000 ^b	Cr^{3+}	1000
Mo^{6+}	1000 ^b	Mo^{6+}	1000
W^{6+}	1000 ^b	W^{6+}	1000
Ti^{4+}	600 ^c	Ti^{4+}	1000
U^{6+}	1000	U^{6+}	800
Ga^{3+}	1500 ^b	Ga^{3+}	1000
Th^{4+}	1000 ^b	Th^{4+}	1000
Cu^{2+}	1500 ^d	Cu^{2+}	1500
Rh^{3+}	375	Rh^{3+}	800
Pd^{2+}	1000	Pd^{2+}	100
Au^{3+}	1000	Au^{3+}	100
Pt^{4+}	750	Pt^{4+}	75
Ru^{3+}	917	Os^{6+}	825

^a=In presence of phosphate ions. ^c=In presence of fluoride ions.
^b=In presence of tartrate ions. ^d=In presence of EDTA.

of osmium or ruthenium. The tolerance limits for the various diverse ions as given in Table 2, represent the concentration of foreign ions in presence of which the transmittance of the extracts of the metal complexes was within $\pm 2\%$.

Simultaneous determination of osmium and ruthenium in a mixture :

A mixture containing 212.25 μg of osmium(VI) and 183.40 μg of ruthenium(III) was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel. The acidity of the mixture was then adjusted to 1-2 M with respect of hydrochloric acid, 2 ml of 0.01 M ethanolic solution of N-benzoyl-N'-methylphenyl selenourea were added and ruthenium was determined as described in the procedure. The pH of the aqueous layer was then adjusted to 5. To this 3 ml of 0.01 M reagent solution were added and osmium was determined as described above.

Accuracy and precision :

The relative mean errors and relative standard deviations for the determination of osmium and ruthenium at different concentrations of the metals are shown in Table 3. The results were obtained from sets of ten experiments under optimum conditions.

TABLE 3—ACCURACY AND PRECISION

Metal ion taken $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Metal ion found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Relative mean error%	Relative standard deviation%
Ruthenium(III)			
(1) 2.20	2.21	+0.45%	0.66%
(2) 3.67	3.66	-0.27%	0.90%
Osmium			
(1) 6.02	6.00	-0.33%	0.88%
(2) 12.04	12.07	+0.25%	0.66%

* Average of ten measurements under identical conditions.

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